

CLINICAL MONITORING PROCESSES AND TREATMENT METHODS OF LUMBAR SPINE FRACTURES: A SINGLE-CENTER EXPERIENCE

Keywords

Thoracolumbar fracture,

Spine injury,

Classification

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ABSTRACT

Although spinal fractures are not the most common type of trauma in the adult population, it is a very important type of trauma due to its seriousness and the socioeconomic and psychological burden it brings. There is a wide range of treatment options for spine fractures, ranging from advanced stabilisation and decompression surgery to clinical monitoring.

In this study, demographic data, fracture aetiology, treatment modalities and neurological status of patients admitted to our clinic with lumbar spine fractures in the last one year were evaluated. Between January 2024 and January 2025, 98 patients admitted with lumbar spine fractures were retrospectively evaluated. Patients were divided into three groups as those who received surgical stabilisation, kyphoplasty and conservative (brace) treatment. Patients with weakness on neurological examination were analysed separately. Of the 98 patients, 41 were female (41.8%) and 57 were male (58.2%). The causes of fracture were 22 (22.4%) osteoporotic fractures, 36 (36.7%) traffic accidents and 40 (40.8%) falls. Surgical stabilisation was performed in 34 (34.7%), kyphoplasty in 18 (18.3%) and conservative treatment with bracing in 44 (44.9%) patients. Loss of motor strength ranging from 0/5 to 3/5 was found in 6 (17.6%) of the stabilised patients. Five of these patients (83.3%) were transported to the hospital by the vehicle of the people who helped them.

The etiology, neurological status of the patient and the type of mobilisation are determinative in the choice of treatment method for lumbar spine fractures. It is noteworthy that a significant proportion of patients, especially those with loss of strength, are not brought to hospital under appropriate transfer conditions

INTRODUCTION

Fractures of the thoracic and lumbar region are caused by high-energy trauma. Therefore, most of the patients present to the health institution as polytraumatised. Failure to recognise the spine fracture in such polytraumatised patients, transfer procedures not performed under appropriate conditions, failure to select appropriate surgical intervention may lead to spinal cord injury or aggravation of neurological damage. Therefore, in polytraumatised patients, it is necessary to act as if there is spinal damage until proven otherwise and plan interventions accordingly. Neurological status, spinal stability, deformity and other injuries should be taken into consideration for treatment. The main aim of treatment should be to limit or even prevent neurological damage, to provide spinal stability, to minimise loss of movement and to prepare the ground for rehabilitation. Although thoracolumbar trauma ranks 21st among all adult traumas, it is of great importance due to its economic, psychological and social consequences. The incidence of spinal trauma is 43.3-51/million people per year in the USA and 12.7/million people in our country. It is more common in males with a ratio of 2.5/1.¹ The most common age range is 30-50 years (45%) and the most common causes are motor vehicle accidents (40%), falls from height (20%), falls from the ground (10%), occupational accidents (18%) and sports injuries (4%).² Stability is very important in the treatment of thoracolumbar fractures. Compression fractures in the anterior column in which the posterior ligament and posterior column are intact are considered stable and are usually treated conservatively. In fractures involving the posterior ligament, posterior column and mid-column, the possibility of neurological deficit is quite high and they are considered unstable and referred for surgical treatment.^{1,2,3,4,5,6,9}

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

This retrospective study included 98 patients with thoracolumbar spine fractures admitted to our clinic between January 2024 and January 2025. Age, gender, fracture etiology (osteoporotic, traffic accident, fall), treatment method (stabilisation, kyphoplasty, bracing), and neurological examination findings (loss of motor strength) were recorded.

RESULTS

Gender Distribution: 41 women (41.8%), 57 men (58.2%) Age distribution 42.3 years (mean age 46.8 years for females and 37.8 years for males)

Etiology of Fracture:

Osteoporotic 22 (%22,4)

Traffic accident 36 (%36,7)

Fall: 40 (40.8%)

Treatment Distribution:

Stabilisation: 34 patients (34.7%)

Kyphoplasty 18 patients (18.3%)

Follow-up with corset: 44 patients (44.9%)

Neurological Findings:

0/5 - 3/5 strength loss in 6 (17.6%) of the patients who underwent stabilisation

Table1. Denis Tracholumbar Fracture Classification^{7,8}

Minor Fractures	
1	Isolated articular process fractures
2	Transverse process fractures
3	Spinous process fractures
4	Pars interarticular fractures
Major Fractures	
1	Compression fractures
2	Blast fractures
3	Flexion Distraction (seat belt) fractures
4	Fractured dislocations

Figure 1. AOSpine thoracolumbar injury classification scoring¹¹

Tip A Compression Fractures		
A0	injury that does not compromise the structural integrity of the spine	0
A1	a single end plate holding the broken bone without affecting the posterior wall	1
A2	fracture that does not affect the posterior wall and holds both end plates	2
A3	broken holding the rear wall and holding a single end plate (incomplete burst)	3
A4	broken holding the rear wall and holding both end plates (complet burst)	5
Tip B Tension band injuries		
B1	complete bone tension band injury	5
B2	Posterior tension band injury	6
B3	Anterior tension band injury	7
Tip C Translational Injury		
C	injury causing translocation of the vertebral body	8

Figure 2. AOSpine thoracolumbar injury classification scoring status and qualifiers¹¹

Neurological Status		
N0	No neurological injury. 100% functional.	0
N1	recovered temporary neurological injury	1
N2	nerve root injury	2
N3	Incomplet Spinal cord injury or Cauda equina syndrome	4
N4	complet spinal cord injury	4
Nx	reliable neurological examination not possible	3
Patient-specific characteristics		
M1	PLK integrity unclear	1
M2	conditions that may affect the patient's specific treatment	0

DISCUSSION

Lumbar spine fractures are common in elderly osteoporotic patients and in high-energy traumas. In this study, especially falls and traffic accidents were the most common traumas. From the initial evaluation to the selection of treatment, patients should be intervened by considering that they have absolute spinal damage, and accurate classification should be made with imaging studies in order to select the appropriate treatment approach. The first classification was made by Watson-Jones in 1938.⁷ In 1983, Francis Denis presented the three-column theory and classified the fractures of the thoracolumbar region into 2 groups as major and minör.^{8,9} (Table 1). In 2013, Vaccar, Magerl et al. revised the thoracolumbar injury classification scoring and published the AOSpine TLBK classification (TLAOSIS).¹⁰

The fact that most of the patients with loss of strength were brought to the hospital under unprofessional conditions reveals the importance of appropriate first intervention and transfer.

CONCLUSION

Multidisciplinary approach and appropriate patient transfer are vital in the treatment of lumbar spine fractures. Available data suggest that not only the type of fracture but also factors such as the mode of transfer and the initial neurological status of the

patient should be taken into consideration in the selection of treatment modalities.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

REFERENCES

1. Bracken MB, Shepard MJ, Holford TR, Leo Summers L, Aldrich EF, Fazl M et al. Administration of methylprednisolone for 24 or 48 hours or tirilazad mesylate for 48 hours in the treatment of acute spinal cord injury. Results of the Third National Acute Spinal Cord Injury Randomised Controlled Trial. National Acute Spinal Cord Injury Study. *JAMA* 1997;277(20):1597-604.
2. Katsura Y, Osborn JM, Cason GW, : The epidemiology of thoracolumbar trauma: A meta-analysis. *J Orthop* 13 (4):383-388,2016
3. .Gnanenthiran SR, Adie S, Harris IA: Nonoperative versus operative treatment for thoracolumbar burst fractures without neurologic deficit: A meta-analysis. *Clin Orthop Relat Res* 470(2):567-577, 2012
4. Hitchon PW, Torner JC, Haddad SF, Follett KA: Management options in thoracolumbar burst fractures. *Surg Neurol* 49(6):619-627, 1998
5. Shen WJ, Shen YS: Nonsurgical treatment of threecolumn thoracolumbar junction burst fractures without neurologic deficit. *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)* 24(4):412- 415, 1999
6. .Siebenga J, Leferink VJM, Segers MJM, Elzinga MJ, Bakker FC, Haarman HJThM, Rommens PM, Duis HJ, Patka P: Treatment of traumatic thoracolumbar spine fractures: A multicenter prospective randomised study of operative versus nonsurgical treatment. *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)* 31(25):2881-2890, 2006
7. Watson-Jones R: The results of postural reduction of fractures of the spine. *J Bone Joint Surg Am* 20(3):567-586, 1938
8. Denis F: The three column spine and its significance in the classification of acute thoracolumbar spinal injuries. *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)* 8(8):817-831, 1983
9. Patel AA, Vaccaro AR: Thoracolumbar spine trauma classification. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg* 18(2):63-71, 2010
10. Vaccaro AR, Oner C, Kepler CK, Dvorak M, Schnake K, Bellabarba C, Reinhold M, Aarabi B, Kandziora F, Chapman J, Shanmuganathan R, Fehlings M, Vialle L: AOSpine thoracolumbar spine injury classification system: Fracture description, neurological status, and key modifiers. *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)* 38(23):2028-2037, 2013
11. Erkan S: Current classifications of thoracolumbar spine fractures. *TOTBID Journal* 17:534-538, 2018